

Table S1: Aquatic exotic species recorded as occurring in the southern portion of the Patos Lagoon, including the Patos Lagoon estuary, São Gonçalo channel, northern Mirim Lagoon and adjacent marine coast.

Taxonomic classification	Vernacular name	Reference and occurrence
KINGDON CHROMISTA		
PHYLUM BACILLARIOPHYTA		
Coscinodiscophyceae		
Coscinodiscales		
Coscinodiscaceae		
<i>Coscinodiscus wailesii</i> (Gran & Angst, 1931)	Diatom	(Odebrecht et al. 2020) (32°01'S, 52°06'W)
PHYLUM MYZOOZOA		
Dinophyceae		
Gonyaulacales		
Ostreopsidaceae		
<i>Alexandrium tamarense</i> (Balech, 1995)	Dinoflagellate	(Odebrecht et al. 1997) (32°11'S, 52°08'W)*
KINGDON ANIMALIA		
PHYLUM ARTHOPODA		
Hexanauplia		
Calanoida		
Temoridae		
<i>Temora turbinata</i> (Dana, 1849)	Copepod	(Muxagata & Gloeden, 1995) (32°08'S, 52°06'W)
Malacostraca		
Decapoda		
Panopeidae		
<i>Rhithropanopeus harrisi</i> (Gould, 1841)	Crab	(D'Incao & Martins, 1998) (31°57'S, 52°05'W)*
Malacostraca		
Decapoda		
Peaeidae		
<i>Metapenaeus monocerus</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	Tiger shrimp	(D'Incao, 1995) (33°25'S, 50°47'W)
Maxillopoda		
Sessilia		
Balanidae		
<i>Megabalanus coccopoma</i> (Darwin, 1854)	Barnacle	(Young, 1995) (32°09'S, 52°02'W)*
PHYLUM BRYOZOA		
Gymnolaemata		
Cheilostomata		
Sinoflustridae		
<i>Membraniporopsis tubigera</i> (Osburn, 1940)	Bryozoan	(Gappa et al. 2010) (32°14'S, 52°10'W)

PHYLUM CNIDARIA

Hydrozoa

Anthoathecata

Hydractiniidae

***Cnidostoma fallax* Vanhoffen, 1911**

Hydromedusa

(Teixeira Amaral et al.
2017)
(32°08'S, 52°06'W)

Moerisiidae

***Moerisia inkermanica* Paltschikoma-
Ostroumawa, 1925**

Hydromedusa

(Teixeira Amaral et al.
2021)
(32°08'S, 52°06'W)

Leptothecata

Blackfordiidae

***Blackfordia virginica* Mayer, 1910**

Hydromedusa

(Teixeira Amaral et al.
2017)
(32°08'S, 52°06'W)

PHYLUM MOLLUSCA

Bivalvia

Mytiloidea

Mytilidae

***Limnoperna fortunei* (Dunker, 1857)**

Golden mussel

(Capítoli &
Bemvenuti, 2005)
(31°56'S, 52°23'W)*

Veneroidea

Corbiculidae

***Corbicula fluminea* (O.F. Muler, 1774)**

Asian clam

(Mansur et al. 1988)
(32°29'S, 52°35'W)*

Gastropoda

Neogastropoda

Muricidae

***Rapana venosa* (Valenciennes, 1846)**

(Spotorno et al. 2020)
(33°31'S, 53°05'W)

PHYLUM CHORDATA

Actinopterygii

Acipenseriformes

Acipenseridae

***Acipenser gueldenstaedtii* (Von Brandt &
Ratzeburg, 1833)**

Russian sturgeon

(Chuctaya et al. 2019)
(32°06'S, 52°04'W)

Characiformes

Acestrorhynchidae

***Acestrorhynchus pantaneiro* (Menezes,
1992)**

Dogfish

(Einhardt et al. 2014)
(32°14'S, 52°49'W)

Serrasalminidae

***Pygocentrus nattereri* Kner, 1858**

Red piranha

(Diário Popular, 2023)
(31°23'S, 51°57'W)*

Cypriniformes

Cyprinidae

***Ctenopharyngodon idella* (Valenciennes,
1844)**

Grass carp

(Garcia et al. 2004)
(32°11'S, 52°04'W)*

***Cyprinus carpio* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Common carp

(Garcia et al. 2004)
(32°31'S, 52°46'W)*

	<i>Hypophthalmichthys nobilis</i> (Richardson, 1845)	Bighead carp	(Garcia et al. 2004) (32°01'S, 52°05'W)*
	<i>H. molitrix</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	Silver carp	(Garcia et al. 2004) (32°02'S, 52°03'W)*
Perciformes			
Sciaenidae			
	<i>Pachyurus bonariensis</i> (Steindachner, 1876)	River croaker	(Harayashiki et al. 2014) (31°47'S, 52°11'W)*
Salmoniformes			
Salmonidae			
	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i> (Walbaum, 1792)		(30°45'S, 51°21'W)*
Siluriformes			
Auchenipteridae			
	<i>Trachelyopterus lucenai</i> (Bertoletti, Pezzi da Silva & Pereira, 1995)	Porrudo, Penharol	(Garcia et al. 2006) (32°29'S, 52°36'W)*
Ictaluridae			
	<i>Ictalurus punctatus</i> (Rafinesque, 1818)	Channel catfish	(Hórus, 2023) (32°02'S, 52°05'W)
Amphibia			
Anura			
Ranidae			
	<i>Aquarana catesbeiana</i> (Shaw, 1802)	Bullfrog	(Xavier & Volcan, 2009) (32°01'S, 52°05'W)
Reptilia			
Testudines			
Emydidae			
	<i>Trachemys scripta</i> (Schoepff, 1792)	Rough turtle	(Hórus, 2023) (32°01'S, 52°05'W)

* Approximate location.